

Table 3: Summary of marine animals recorded from baited remote underwater videos (BRUVs) conducted in Toki, Natubari and Nalulu passages

IUCN world status abbreviations: LC = Least Concern, **VU = Vulnerable**, **NT = Near Threatened**, **EN = Endangered**, **CR = Critically Endangered**

Passage	Common_name	Fijian_name	Taxonomy	IUCN Status	Raw Count	Attracted bait	Bite bait	Depth (m)	Tide	Current strength	Habitat type
Toki	Yellowmask surgeonfish	Balagi	<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	LC	3	No	No	20.8	Flow	Low	Reef
	Spanish mackerel	Walu	<i>Scomberomorus commerson</i>	NT	2	No	No	20.8 - 64	Flow	Low – Moderate	Open & Reef
	Humphead wrasse	Varivoce	<i>Cheilinus undulatus</i>	EN	2	No	No	20.8 - 25	Flow	Low	Reef
	Blackfin barracuda	Sasanitoga / Ogo	<i>Sphyaena qenie</i>	LC	18	Yes	No	34.8 - 64	Flow	Moderate	Open
	Milkspotted puffer	Sumusumu	<i>Chelonodontops patoca</i>	LC	1	Yes	No	30	Ebb	Moderate	Open
	Grey reef shark	Qio rewasaga	<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	EN	2	Yes	No	30	Ebb	Moderate	Open
	Batfish	Latinidaveta	<i>Platax sp.</i>	LC	7	No	No	39.5	Ebb & Flow	Low	Open
	Hammerhead shark	Qio ulutuki	<i>Sphyrna sp.</i>	CR	3	No	No	36.2	Flow	Moderate	Open
	Barracuda	Ogo	<i>Sphyaena sp.</i>	LC	1	No	No	36.2	Flow	Moderate	Open
	Silvertip shark	Qio dina	<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	VU	2	Yes	No	36.2	Flow	Moderate	Open
	Cornetfish	Baba	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	LC	1	No	No	15	Ebb	Low	Open
	Green sea turtle	Vonu	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	LC	2	No	No	15	Ebb	Low	Open
	Golden trevally	Vilu	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	LC	1	No	No	15	Ebb	Low	Open
	Double-lined mackerel	Salalanitoga	<i>Grammatorcynus bilineatus</i>	LC	18	No	No	15 - 20.5	Ebb & Flow	Low – Moderate	Open & Reef
	Yellowband Parrotfish	Kakarawa	<i>Scarus schlegeli</i>	LC	1	No	No	20.5	Flow	Moderate	Reef
	Black-blotch Porcupinefish	Sokisoki	<i>Diodon liturosus</i>	LC	1	No	No	20.5	Flow	Moderate	Reef
	Moray eel	Dabea	<i>Gymnothorax sp.</i>	LC	1	No	No	20.5	Flow	Moderate	Reef
	Barcheek trevally	Saqa / Tokadrau	<i>Craterognathus plagiotaenia</i>	LC	1	No	No	25	Flow	Low	Reef
	Milk fish	Yawa	<i>Chanos chanos</i>	LC	1	No	No	25	Flow	Low	Reef
	Coral grouper	Donu	<i>Plectropomus sp.</i>	LC	1	No	No	25	Flow	Low	Reef
	Parrotfish	Ulavi	Scaridae	LC	4	No	No	25	Flow	Low	Reef
	Elongate unicornfish	Ta	<i>Naso lopezii</i>	LC	2	No	No	17	Ebb	Moderate	Reef
	Trevally	Saqa	Carangidae	LC	7	No	No	17	Ebb	Moderate	Reef
	Natubari	Yellowmask surgeonfish	Balagi	<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	LC	9	No	No	17	Ebb & Flow	Low – moderate
Ocellated eagle ray		Vai vuka	<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>	EN	5	No	No	17	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Eagle ray		Vaibeka	<i>Aetobatus sp.</i>	EN	2	No	No	44.3	Ebb	Strong	Open
Orange-lined triggerfish		Cumu	<i>Balistapus undulatus</i>	LC	1	Yes	Yes	20	Flow	Moderate	Reef-slope
Blue-and-yellow fusilier		Tikawa	<i>Caesio teres</i>	LC	260	No	No	12 - 44.3	Ebb & Flow	Low – Strong	Open & Reef-slope
Trevally		Saqa	Carangidae	LC	30	No	No	30	Ebb	Low	Open
Bluefin trevally		Saqanivatu / Tauta	<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	LC	4	No	No	17	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Brassy trevally		Wainikodro	<i>Caranx papuensis</i>	LC	65	Yes	No	17 - 20	Ebb & Flow	Low – Moderate	Reef-slope
Silvertip shark		Qio dina	<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	VU	1	No	No	20	Flow	Moderate	Reef-slope
Requiem shark		Qio	<i>Carcharhinus sp.</i>	NT-EN	2	No	No	18	Ebb	Low	Rubble-slope
Black-tip reef shark		Qio	<i>Carcharhinus melanopterus</i>	VU	1	No	No	20	Flow	Moderate	Reef-slope
Sunburst butterflyfish		Daliga ragutu / Tivitivi	<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i>	LC	4	Yes	Yes	20	Ebb & Flow	Low – Moderate	Reef-slope
Raccoon butterflyfish		Daliga ragutu / Tivitivi	<i>Chaetodon lunula</i>	LC	4	Yes	No	Shallow	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Double saddle butterflyfish		Daliga ragutu / Tivitivi	<i>Chaetodon ulietensis</i>	LC	4	Yes	Yes	20	Ebb & Flow	Low – Moderate	Reef-slope
Humphead wrasse		Varivoce	<i>Cheilinus undulatus</i>	EN	6	No	No	18	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Humphead wrasse (Female)		Varivoce	<i>Cheilinus undulatus</i>	EN	1	No	No	17	Flow	Low	Reef-slope
Weber's chromis		Guru	<i>Chromis weberi</i>	LC	30	Yes	No	20	Flow	Moderate	Reef-slope
Barcheek trevally		Saqa / Tokadrau	<i>Craterognathus plagiotaenia</i>	LC	23	Yes	No	17 - 20	Ebb & Flow	Low – Moderate	Reef-slope
Threespot dascyllus		Guru	<i>Dascyllus trimaculatus</i>	LC	5	Yes	No	17	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Spotfin porcupinefish		Sokisoki	<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	LC	1	No	No	Shallow	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Hawksbill sea turtle		Vonu	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	CR	1	No	No	18	Ebb	Low	Rubble-slope
Golden trevally		Vilu	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	LC	1	No	No	12	Ebb	Moderate	Rubble
Double-lined mackerel		Salalanitoga	<i>Grammatorcynus bilineatus</i>	LC	6	No	No	44.3	Ebb & Flow	Low – Strong	Open & Reef-slope
Japanese large-eye bream		Sabutu	<i>Gymnocranius euanus</i>	LC	4	Yes	Yes	12	Ebb	Moderate	Rubble
Pennet coralfish		Tivitivi	<i>Heniochus accuminatus</i>	LC	9	Yes	Yes	17 - 20	Ebb-Flow	Low – Moderate	Reef-slope
Emperor		Sabutu	Lethrinidae	LC	12	No	No	12	Ebb	Low – Moderate	Reef-slope
Thumbprint emperor		Kabatia	<i>Lethrinus harak</i>	LC	1	No	No	12	Ebb	Moderate	Rubble
Emperor		Sabutu	<i>Lethrinus sp.</i>	LC	1	No	No	17	Flow	Low	Reef-slope
Blacktail snapper		Tanabe / Dadriu / Kake	<i>Lutjanus fulvus</i>	LC	1	No	No	17	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Big-eye bream		Bu / Mama	<i>Monotaxis grandoculis</i>	LC	1	Yes	Yes	Shallow	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Blotcheye soldierfish		Corocoro	<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	LC	3	No	No	17	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Grey unicornfish		Ta	<i>Naso caesius</i>	LC	20	No	No	17	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Sleek unicornfish		Ta	<i>Naso haxacanthus</i>	LC	13	No	No	17	Ebb & Flow	Low	Reef-slope
Unicornfish		Ta	<i>Naso sp.</i>	LC	5	No	No	30	Ebb	Low	Open
Redtooth triggerfish		Cumu	<i>Odonus niger</i>	LC	90	Yes	Yes	17	Ebb & Flow	Low	Reef-slope
Dash-and-dot goatfish		Cucu / Ose	<i>Parupeneus barberinus</i>	LC	1	No	No	12	Ebb	Moderate	Rubble
Manybar goatfish		Cucu / Ose	<i>Parupeneus multifasciatus</i>	LC	1	Yes	No	Shallow	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
Golden spadefish		Latinidaveta	<i>Platax boersii</i>	LC	6	Yes	No	17	Flow	Low	Reef-slope
Obicular batfish		Latinidaveta	<i>Platax orbicularis</i>	LC	11	Yes	No	20 - 40	Ebb & Flow	Moderate – Strong	Open & Reef-slope
Batfish		Latinidaveta	<i>Platax sp.</i>	LC	5	No	No	30	Ebb	Low	Open & Reef-slope
Damselfish	Guru	Pomacentridae	LC	2	Yes	Yes	Shallow	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope	
Jobfish	Pakapaka	<i>Pristipomoides sp.</i>	LC	1	No	No	17	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope	
Blue-and-gold fusilier	Sila	<i>Pterocaesio caeruleaurea</i>	LC	3	Yes	No	Shallow	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope	
Banana fusilier	Sila	<i>Pterocaesio pisang</i>	LC	6	Yes	No	17	Ebb & Flow	Low	Reef-slope	
Three-stripe fusilier	Sila	<i>Pterocaesio trilineata</i>	LC	30	No	No	17	Ebb & Flow	Low	Reef-slope	
Bridled parrotfish	Kakarawa	<i>Scarus frenatus</i>	LC	1	No	No	12	Ebb	Moderate	Rubble	
Yellowband parrotfish	Kakarawa	<i>Scarus schlegeli</i>	LC	2	No	No	12	Ebb	Moderate	Rubble	
Doublespotted queenfish	Votonimoli / Lai	<i>Scomberoides lysan</i>	LC	4	No	No	Shallow	Flow	Low – Moderate	Open	
Queenfish	Votonimoli / Lai	<i>Scomberoides sp.</i>	LC	2	No	No	30	Ebb	Low	Open	
Spanish mackerel	Walu	<i>Scomberomorus commerson</i>	NT	4	Yes	No	40	Ebb & Flow	Moderate – Strong	Open	
Pickhandle barracuda	Ogobuidromo	<i>Sphyaena jello</i>	LC	15	Yes	No	Shallow	Flow	Moderate	Open	
Blackfin barracuda	Sasanitoga / Ogo	<i>Sphyaena qenie</i>	LC	93	Yes	No	18 - 44.3	Ebb & Flow	Low – Strong	Open & Reef-slope	
Moon wrasse	Drividrivi	<i>Thalassoma lunare</i>	LC	6	Yes	No	17-20	Ebb-Flow	Low – Moderate	Reef-slope	
Snubnose dart	Qawaqawa / Lalitarawau	<i>Trachinotus blachii</i>	LC	2	No	No	18	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope	
White-tip reef shark	Qio dina	<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	VU	4	No	No	18	Ebb & Flow	Low – Moderate	Reef-slope	
Nalulu	Ocellated eagle ray	Vai vuka	<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>	EN	7	No	No	36.7	Flow	Moderate	Sand & Reef-slope
	African pompano	Saqa dreve	<i>Alectis ciliaris</i>	LC	1	No	No	34.3	Flow	Moderate	Sand
	Brassy trevally	Wainikodro	<i>Caranx papuensis</i>	LC	3	Yes	No	34.3	Flow	Moderate	Reef-slope
	Grey reef shark	Qio rewasaga	<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	EN	3	Yes	Yes	28 - 34.7	Ebb	Strong	Open & Reef-slope
	Requiem shark	Qio	<i>Carcharhinus sp.</i>	NT-EN	1	No	No	26	Flow	Low	Reef-slope
	Double saddle butterflyfish	Daliga ragutu / Tivitivi	<i>Chaetodon ulietensis</i>	LC	3	Yes	Yes	17.8	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
	Barcheek trevally	Saqa / Tokadrau	<i>Craterognathus plagiotaenia</i>	LC	6	No	No	36.7	Flow	Moderate	Reef-slope
	Striated surgeonfish	Meto	<i>Ctenochaetus striatus</i>	LC	1	No	No	17.8	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
	Malabar grouper	Soisoi	<i>Epinephelus malabaricus</i>	LC	1	No	No	17.8	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
	Moray eel	Dabea	<i>Gymnothorax sp.</i>	LC	1	Yes	Yes	17.8	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
	Semicircle angelfish	Latinidaveta	<i>Pomacanthus semicirculatus</i>	LC	2	No	No	24.4 - 36.7	Ebb & Flow	Moderate – Strong	Reef-slope
	Black-banded snapper	Kaka	<i>Lutjanus semicinctus</i>	LC	2	No	No	24.4	Ebb	Strong	Reef-slope
	Emperor	Sabutu	Lethrinidae	LC	1	No	No	34.7	Ebb	Low	Sand
	Twospot snapper	Kake	<i>Lutjanus biguttatus</i>	LC	2	No	No	17.8 - 24.4	Ebb	Low – Strong	Reef-slope
	Blacktail snapper	Tanabe / Dadriu / Kake	<i>Lutjanus fulvus</i>	LC	4	No	No	17.8 - 24.4	Ebb	Low – Strong	Reef-slope
	Blotcheye soldierfish	Corocoro	<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	LC	11	No	No	17.8	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
	Golden spadefish	Latinidaveta	<i>Platax boersii</i>	LC	1	No	No	24.4	Ebb	Strong	Reef-slope
	Coral grouper	Donu	<i>Plectropomus sp.</i>	LC	10	No	No	24.4	Ebb	Strong	Reef-slope
	Banana fusilier	Sila	<i>Pterocaesio pisang</i>	LC	4	No	No	17.8	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
	Regal angelfish	Tivitivi	<i>Pygoplites diacanthus</i>	LC	1	No	No	17.8	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
	Silverspot squirrelfish	Dravisau / Draveisau	<i>Sargocentron caudimaculatum</i>	LC	1	Yes	Yes	24.4	Ebb	Strong	Reef-slope
	Parrotfish	Ulavi	Scaridae	LC	1	No	No	17.8	Ebb	Low	Reef-slope
	Queenfish	Votonimoli / Lai	<i>Scomberomoides sp.</i>	LC	1	Yes	No	34.3	Flow	Moderate	Sand
	Pickhandle barracuda	Ogobuidromo	<i>Sphyaena jello</i>	LC	10	Yes	No	19.2 - 34.7	Ebb	Low – Strong	Reef-slope
Hammerhead shark	Qio ulutuki	<i>Sphyrna sp.</i>	CR	2	No	No	34.3	Flow	Moderate	Reef-slope	
Round ribbontail ray	Vai	<i>Taeniura meyeni</i>	VU	10	No	No	34.3	Flow	Moderate	Reef-slope	
Snubnose dart	Qawaqawa / Lalitarawau	<i>Trachinotus blachii</i>	LC	1	No	No	36.7	Flow	Moderate	Reef-slope	
White-tip reef shark	Qio dina	<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	VU	3	Yes	No	17.8	Ebb	Low – Strong	Reef-slope	